

SYED QAIM ALI SHAH: SOCIO-ECONOMIC SERVICES AT DISTRICT KHAIRPUR AS CHIEF MINISTER OF SINDH, PAKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

The most prominent personality of District Khairpur, Sindh – Pakistan namely; Syed Qaim Ali Shah's service as Sindh's Chief Minister (2008–2013; 2013–2016) generated substantial socio-economic progress across the province. His administration executed transformative initiatives in much different fields especially; in healthcare, farming, education, transit systems, and civic infrastructure. The notable accomplishments are included here as in founding the different universities located at province of Sindh, agricultural modules, medical centers, research labs, public libraries, economic zones, job programs, housing colonies, veterinary facilities, auditoriums, and the Individual Scheme, Infrastructure advancements featured prominently, particularly through three overhead bridges and eleven canal bridges in and around the district Khairpur Mir's. Beyond establishing institutions, Shah's government ensured their operational efficacy and service delivery at the home step. This commitment markedly enhanced facilities for Khairpur's residents and neighboring communities, cementing his legacy of enduring regional development not only at province level but also at the Pakistan level.

Keywords: Agriculture, Date palm area, Insecticide free zone, Education, and Socioeconomic.

INTRODUCTION

Syed Qaim Ali Shah's visionary initiatives in his home district provided enduring benefits, establishing a blueprint for parliamentary representatives. Dedicated leadership enables transformative constituent development, fostering lasting public esteem. Born September 13, 1933, into an esteemed Syed lineage, Shah received foundational education at Government Naz Pilot School, Khairpur (Sahito et al., 2025), further he is well known personality who has served as CM of Sindh which is remarkable service of the Shah.

During 1961 local elections, Shah secured the Vice Chairmanship, initiating impactful civic work. He mobilized teams to reclaim the Raboou Ji Khad landfill and launched citywide sanitation

campaigns starting in Luqman Muhalla. This inspired youth-led community groups, catalyzing Sachal Academy's formation with Shah as Vice President—foundations for Khairpur's sustained growth. Consequently; he has established the Sachal Sarmast fair in which the events and articles were refreshed thus; the political discussions were regularly included at his residence located at district Khairpur in which the socio cultural and political activities were cordially hosted and managed at his proper way to continue his political activities on ward.

His administration launched pivotal economic ventures: The Sindh Investment Board attracted capital from 54+ nations. Key programs included

Sindh Bank, Sindh Small Industries, Thar Coal Project, and Shaheed Benazir Bhutto Housing. Farmers received land, training, machinery (including tractors), while new Schools, Colleges, and Universities were constructed. Road networks were also expanded by thousands of kilometers alongside industrial units combating unemployment. Further measures encompassed the Benazir Income Support Program, watercourse projects, youth technical training, Shaheed Benazir Bhutto Youth Development, Sindh Education Foundation, and Country Development Programs. Literally, Shah always says that he feels as he is not as old as not fight any election on his fascinating and smile with his happy face as he contested at the age of ninety years an old. As the criticism, he is some time said to be the very old but he always replied them, old is gold but due to the veteran in the field of politics he is able to manage the thinks as proper way hence; he fought many of the politician elections in the province of Sindh. Therefore, he might be said that he stood as the most and prominent, a loyal versatile politician among his contemporaries at the provincial and national personalities of Sindh and Pakistan. Hence; it was dire need to keep research study on this great politician to be nominated much and more to be remained in the heart of people's province of Sindh, Pakistan or at the world wide, meanwhile the objectives are described as under with detailed nutshell.

Objectives

1. Implement low-cost housing (115,494 families) and modern sewerage in 1,076 villages to elevate living standards.
2. Establish the Sindh Investment Board via collaboration with industrialist Mohammad Zubair Motiwala.
3. Modernize sectors through Education City Khairpur, Khairpur Special Economic Zone (KSEZ), Thar Coal, renewable energy, livestock, agriculture, drip irrigation, and export-oriented mango/meat/dairy production.
4. Launch new budgetary programs alongside the 2025 development strategy.
5. Found Shaheed Benazir Bhutto University of Veterinary and Animal Sciences (Sakrand/Larkana; Rs. 1.027+ billion).

Hypothesis

The hypothesis concerned with Syed Qaim Ali Shah identified him as prominent social reformer of district Khairpur when he was need of time in office as Chief Minister of Sindh province. The first study was carried out over his biography and life career. Later on, this study was carried out through his tenure when he was CM, regarding the working efficiencies and struggling carrier as a politician of district, Khairpur, Sindh Pakistan. Thus the research aimed to analyze his contributions and challenges faced as a politician in the region of Sindh, Pakistan.

Research Methodology

The depicted study of prominent personality of Sindh, Pakistan and throughout world is an exploratory and analytical examination within a qualitative framework that focuses on the well-known personality, social being and political dimensions, along with other facets of the former Chief Minister of Sindh, Syed Qaim Ali Shah. A case study as defined, serves as a thorough and insightful investigation in to the life of an individual, a group or an organization is crystallized in this research work further defined as under.

During the Field Marshal Mr. Muhammad Ayub Khan with its fundamental democracy where as in 1960, Mr. Shah entered into politics as he become an elected Chairman of Khairpur district council later on, he became very close to Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto Peoples Party very hasty in manner. He became member of provincial assembly, Sindh during, 1990 whereas; he lost his single election in 1997 in his career. He also won 7 as out of the 8 general elections in which he took participated hence; became the MPA, as the 6 times. Subsequently; Mr. Qaim Ali Shah completed the second term as CM of Sindh province during, 2013.

Establishment of mega projects

Shah's administration appointed 165,000 youths permanently in government roles and recruited 27,000 into Sindh Police, reducing crime by 30-40%. Partnering with the World Bank, the Shaheed Benazir Bhutto Youth Development Program trained 200,000 youths; 30% gained

employment, aiding 365,000 families. Expenditures included: People's Development Scheme (Rs. 688 billion), provincial allocation (Rs. 479 billion), foreign aid (Rs. 1,234 billion), district schemes (Rs. 585 billion), and MP-local development (Rs. 30.99 billion). Sectoral investments: Coal (Rs. 30.3B), Industries (Rs. 8B), Roads (Rs. 55B), Irrigation/Agriculture (Rs. 24B), Relief/Rehabilitation (Rs. 41B). Health budgets rose 400% (Rs. 5.2B to Rs. 22B, 2007–2012). Karachi received Rs. 110B (water: Rs. 25B; Liari: Rs. 3.7B; Malir: Rs. 6B; Hyderabad: Rs. 6.8B). Thar water supply secured Rs. 24B via Public Health Engineering.

Results and Discussion

1. Khairpur Development Initiatives

Sukkur Division Development Board allocated Rs. 151.198 million for Khairpur. Shah-era schemes revised included: Kot Lalo-Akri road (Rs. 31.516M), Drib Mehar Shah Playground (Rs. 40M), Kotdiji road rehabilitation (Rs. 39.827M), and Kotdiji repairs (Rs. 39.855M). Commissioner Muhammad Abbas Baloch mandated strict project oversight. Khairpur Medical College and Hospital established not for medical point of view but the recent researches were conducted at the Master and PhD level on dengue and malaria and its control measures (Baloch et al., 2025) and some time the ethno plants usage to recover the damaged cells of papaya plants (Ghumro et al., 2026).

2. Specialized Departments & Social Welfare

New ministries included Minorities Affairs, Sindh Revenue Board, and Women's Development. Technical centers empowered underserved women. Minorities received 5% job quotas, Rs. 930M for worship sites, and Rs. 600M aid. Sindh disbursed cash to 800,000 women and interest-free loans to 100,000 in Tharparkar / Shikarpur / Jacobabad. Flood victims received 7,000 homes; disability/orphan quotas rose with new villages. Gorakh Hill Station achieved international standards. Female job reservations increased from 5% to 25%.

3. Shrines, Dams & Education

Major investments: Lal Shahbaz Qalandar shrine development, Sadh Belo Temple (Rs. 500M), farmer support (tractors, free inputs, loans), and small dams. Education funding grew from Rs. 80B (2007–08) to Rs. 121B, establishing 07 universities, 03 engineering colleges, 09 cadet colleges (02 female), and 03 medical universities. Initiatives included subsidized healthcare, hospital construction, scholarships, free girls' education (to Matric), and international scholarships. Allocations: Wind Energy (Rs. 7.5B), Water/Drainage (Rs. 720M), Minorities (Rs. 720M), Health (Rs. 49.52B), Thar Coal (Rs. 13.585B), Education (Rs. 111.96B). Additional support: Sui Gas (612 villages), aid (334,923 families), loans (103,642), filtered water (108,689 families), health insurance, and 181 schools restored + 547 Katchi Abadis formalized.

4. Political Tenure & 2013 Elections

Shah demonstrated loyalty during the 1983 MRD movement against Zia, operating underground. As Sindh PPP President (1987) and later CM (1988), he served 13 months initially. His second term confronted Karachi's security challenges but completed five years.

5. Shaheed Benazir Bhutto Housing Scheme

Launched November 13, 2012, near Luqman, Khairpur, this scheme distributed free plots (Rs. 400,000–500,000 value) with amenities under PPP's "Roti, Kapra aur Makan." The 80-acre project (Rs. 234.639M) included 1,530 plots (188 commercial), plus dedicated sites for mosques (3), schools (3), community centers (3), a hospital, vocational institute, and 8 parks. Plot allocation occurred via lottery managed by Commissioner Baloch and Syed Manzar Abbas.

6. Enlisted Departments (Since 2020)

Departments: Electrical, Civil, Mechanical, Petroleum & Natural Gas, Software Engineering, Electronics, BSRS (consolidated faculty data).

7. Sachal Sarmast Government Library

Inaugurated January 8, 2010 (Rs. 390,000), housing 131,000 books for students and CSS/PCS aspirants.

8. Sports Infrastructure Upgrades

Syeda Nafisa Shah secured federal funds: Mumtaz Ground (Rs. 19.271M), Luqman Hockey Ground (Rs. 8.729M), Shaheed Benazir Bhutto Sports Complex (Rs. 28M).

9. Khairpur Special Economic Zone (KSEZ)

Established under SEZ Act 2012 on 140 acres (PC-I: Rs. 2,174M) for agro-processing. Land use: 83 acres (Industrial), 1.5 acres (Commercial). Sold: 99% (80% local; 11.2% foreign/Chinese). Employs 35 technical staff locally. Aims: 5,000–88,000 direct + 74,000 indirect jobs in date processing. Initiated 2008–09 (Rs. 3,351M planned; Khairpur phase: Rs. 1,487.959M revised to Rs. 1,700M for 136 acres at Tando Nazar Ali). Progress by 2011: Master Plan approved, land acquired, fencing/gate construction initiated. Further, this economic zone is being used to facilitate dry and semi-dry dates to export level quality hence; the date palm growers do best way IPM, strategy to mitigate the pest population in date palm orchards of district Khairpur as suggested and worked by different scientist of the concerned area literally by the (Sahito et al., 2017; Jatoi et al., 2020; Jatoi and Sahito, 2023; Jatoi et al., 2024; Mangrio et al., 2024; Baloch et al., 2025). Infrastructure development (roads, water, and sewage) commenced. A waste-fueled power plant was planned (US tech interest noted) but stalled by SPPRA. KSEZ offers 10-year tax holidays and machinery import exemptions; CPEC status sought. SSGC restrictions affected gas supply.

10. KSEZ Significance & Potential

Khawaja Amer (National Industrial Parks, 2013) identified KSEZ as Pakistan's premier agro-SEZ. Value-added processing in Khairpur (national leader: 329,900 tons dates, 52% output, 2009–10) could reduce waste, raise profits, and boost exports. Harvest Tracings CEO Jawad projected exports rising from \$200M to \$240M annually with enhanced facilities.

11. Sindh Cities Improvement Plan (SCIP)

Responding to Assembly Query 6104, Shah confirmed the ADB-backed SCIP (\$400M) targeted municipal upgrades (water, wastewater, solid waste) via Multi-tranche Financing (2009–2018). Northern Cluster (Sukkur, New Sukkur, Rohri, Khairpur, Shikarpur, and Larkana) was managed by NSUSC (Sukkur HQ), with Jacobabad/Ghotki additions planned under Tranche 2.

12. Khairpur Development Schemes

Per District Government Newsletter (2011), Shah inaugurated 11 schemes (Rs. 540M) for Khairpur Taluka under ADP 2008/2012. Additional projects commenced during his tenures.

Source: Filed Research as the key inaugurated schemes:

1. The Chief Minister Syed Qaim Ali Shah inaugurated the Computerized Domicile Branch on October 24, 2010 at Khairpur.
2. The Chief Minister Syed Qaim Ali Shah inaugurated the District Management Suite and District Security Surveillance in 2010 at Khairpur.
3. The Chief Minister Syed Qaim Ali Shah inaugurated the Thalassemia Centre and Blood Bank at Khairpur.
4. The Chief Minister Syed Qaim Ali Shah inaugurated the Shaheed Benazir Bhutto Housing cell at Khairpur. 200 acres were allotted for this purpose and total 1700 plots were prepared with the estimated Rs: 32 crores for poor families. However, banglows on 85 acres were occupied by different people. 10 thousand people had given applications and out of them after verifications only 2300 poor families were finalized by the DC Khairpur but still they are waiting. This Benazir basiti has facilities of roads, water arrangements, electricity, gas, transformer, drainage system, and boundary wall.
5. The Chief Minister Syed Qaim Ali Shah inaugurated the Shaheed Benazir Bhutto Park at Gosha Taskeen on Tuesday, 18th January costing of Rs 5 3531000 million.
6. The Chief Minister Syed Qaim Ali Shah inaugurated the Bilawal Bhutto Park in 2012 costing of Rs. 4 4688000 million near Bhurguri Regulator and Phool Baag Park at Khairpur.

7. Khairpur Special Economic Zone.
8. Syed Ramazan Shah Trade Centre costing of Rs. 60304000 million.
9. Construction of Khajoor Mandi at Khairpur.
10. Construction of Orphan Centre at Khairpur.
11. Construction of Small Cottage at Khairpur.
12. Construction of Display Centre for Handicrafts at Khairpur.
13. Construction of District Government Secretariat at Khairpur.
14. Construction of Revenue officer House.
15. Construction of Revenue Complex.
16. Rehabilitation of District Medical Dispensary and maternity Home.
17. Construction/Rehabilitation of Veterinary, Dispensary and Centre.
18. Construction of Benazir Bhutto Sports Complex at Khairpur.
19. Construction of Mother and Child Care Centre Khairpur.
20. Construction/Inauguration of High/Higher Secondary Schools
21. Khairpur Tourism Development Project costing Rs. 20 million.
22. Modern Bus Terminal at old SRTC Bus Stop costing of Rs. 87040000 million
23. Skill Development and Learning Centre (SDLC) costing Rs. 2 million.
24. Inauguration of Petroleum Technical Training Institute (PTTI) at Government College of technology Khairpur costing of Rs. 88 million.
25. Inauguration of Inter-road of Government College of technology Khairpur costing of Rs. 15 million.
26. Inauguration of Building for Sachal Sarmast Government Library on January 8, 2010.
27. Mehran University College of Engineering and Technology Khairpur
28. Construction of modern Gymkhana and community Hall costing of Rs. 79644000 million.
29. Construction of two slaughter houses one for city Khairpur and other for Luqman costing of Rs. 8765000 million.
30. Shaheed Benazir Bhutto Open Air Theatre has been completed costing Rs. 40000000 million and inauguration was done on July 1, 2009 with the cultural minister Ms. Sasi Palejo.
31. Establishment of Shaheed Benazir Bhutto Engineering College at Khairpur Mirs estimated cost Rs. 300.000 million, estimated expenditure up to June 2008 Rs. 300.000 50.000 million allocated in 2008-09.
32. Renovation of Faiz Mahal at Khairpur (PM Un-Approved, estimated cost Rs. 1028.485 million in 2008-09.
33. Establishment of SOS Hermann Gmeiner School at SOS Children's Village Khairpur (C:46.828 + R:2.866) (SDG # 4), Approved on 05.06.17 and work should be completed till June-2019. The estimated cost was Rs. 49.694 million. And actual expenditure up to June 2017 was Rs. 49.694 million but it was not completed and revised up to 2019-20.
34. Establishment of Cadet College Khairpur (Revised) (C:1141.114 + R:379.225) (SDG # 4) Khairpur, Approved on 26.04.16, targeted date for completion was June-21 with estimated cost of Rs. 1520.339 million, actual expenditure up to June 2017 was Rs. 338.280 million but it was revised again and again up to 2019-20.
35. Development of New Infrastructure and Other Essential Facilities for Establishment of Mehran University College of Engineering and Technology at Kharipur Mirs (C:597.011 + R:551.003) (SDG # 4), Approved on 19.08.10, targeted date for completion was June-20 with estimated cost of Rs. 1148.014 million and actual date of expenditure cost was Rs. 913.498 million but it was revised and reallocated up to 2017-18.
36. Development of Remaining Essential Facilities Required for Establishment of Mehran University College of Engineering and Technology at Khairpur Mir's (C:717.236 + R:130.492) (SDG # 4), Approved on 28.01.12. The targeted date for completion was June-21 with estimated cost of Rs. 847.728 million and actual date of expenditure cost was Rs. 454.385 million but the allocation was revised for 2017-18.
37. Establishment of Khairpur College of Agriculture and Management Sciences Khairpur Mir's Constituent College of Sindh Agriculture University Tando Jam (Revised) (C: 853.866 + R: 538.647) (SDG # 4), Approved on 31.12.15, targeted date for completion was June-21 with

estimated cost of Rs. 1392.513 million. The actual expenditure up to June 2017 was Rs. 305.126 million but its allocation was also revised up to 2018-19.

38. Establishment of Model School at Shah Abdul Latif University (SALU) Khairpur (Revised) (C: 87.238 + R: 1.960) (SDG # 4), Approved on 03.04.13. Targeted date for completion was June-19 with estimated cost of Rs. 89.198 million. The actual expenditure up to June 2017 was Rs. 80.506 million but the allocation was revised up to 2018-19.

39. Establishment of Shaheed Benazir Bhutto Chair at Shah Abdul Latif University, Khairpur (C:28.766 + R:12.132) (SDG # 4), Approved on 20.03.13. The targeted date for completion was June-20 with estimated cost of Rs. 40.898 million. The actual expenditure up to June 2017 was Rs. 21.793 million but it was revised up to 2018-19.

40. Establishment of IT Institute at IT College Khairpur (C:227.280 + R:190.232) (SDG # 4), Approved on 22.01.13 and targeted date for completion was June-21 and the actual expenditure up to June 2017 was Rs. 417.512 million but allocation was revised up to 2018-19.

41. Establishment of Khairpur Eye Hospital, District Khairpur. (C: 69.149 +R: 38.251) (SDG #3), Approved on 26.04.16 with targeted date for completion was June-19. The estimated cost was Rs. 107.400 million and actual expenditure up to June 2017 was Rs. 11.097 million but the allocation was revised up to 2018-19.

42. Construction of Overhead Bridge over New National Highway at Shah Hussain By-pass Chowk (3922 Rft) (Revised) (SDG # 9), Approved on 03.03.16 and targeted date of completion was June-21 with estimated cost of Rs. 1605.175 million. The actual expenditure up to June 2017 was Rs. 794.861 million but the allocation was revised up to 2018-19 to 2019-20.

43. Construction of Government Dispensary at Village (i) Qadir Bux Jalbani UC Machyoon Taluka and District Khairpur (ii) Hafeez Chandio Taluka Kingri District Khairpur (iii) Kumbai Metlo UC Pir Mangio Taluka and District Khairpur (iv) Pir Bux Metlo UC Morai Taluka and District Khairpur. (C: 18.000+R: 6.000) (SDG # 3), Approved on 17.12.12. The targeted date for completion was June-19 with estimated cost of Rs.

24.000 million and the actual expenditure up to June 2017 was Rs. 10.500 million but it was revised up to 2018-19.

44. Construction of New Building of TB Hospital at Khairpur. (C: 140.690+R: 18.439) (SDG # 3), Approved on 18.02.15. The targeted date for completion was June-20 with estimated cost of Rs. 159.129 million. The actual expenditure up to June 2017 was Rs. 90.360 million but the allocation was revised up to 2018-19.

45. Construction of Heart Centre in Civil Hospital, Khairpur. (C: 203.820+R: 253.360) (SDG # 3), Approved on 18.02.15 with targeted date for completion of June-21. The estimated cost was Rs. 457.180 million with actual expenditure up to June 2017 of Rs. 144.397 million but the allocation was revised up to 2018-19.

46. Construction of Ladies & Children Park at Mir Ali Bazar Khairpur (Branch Higher Secondary School Khairpur) (Revised) (SDG # 8), Approved on 20.04.16 with Targeted date of completion of June-19 and the estimated cost was Rs 20.098 million with actual expenditure up to June 2017 of Rs. 11.835 million but the allocation was revised up to 2018-19.

47. Luqman Bridge was constructed Under Provincial set up but NAB has observed corruption in it.

48. Overhead Bridge at Therhi Phatak was constructed Under District setup.

49. The Benazir Bhutto Shaheed University of Technology and Skill Development (BBSUTSD) Khairpur: Act of the university was passed on 22nd April 2016 by the Sindh Assembly and the admissions for the 1st academic session were announced in 2017-18 in different fields.

50. Khairpur Medical College was established & inaugurated by Syed Qaim Ali Shah chief Minister of Sindh on 29 December 2012. From 12 public sectors medical Colleges of Sindh in which only the Khairpur Medical College, Khairpur registered with the PMDC, allocated with one hundred medical students per year awarding college. Hence; the first candidates' batch was started in session for the 2014-15 which was successfully awarded their degree program. Keeping in scenario, the BPS, based staff is

working from grade one to twenty one as the professorships followed by enlarging day by day.

Conclusion

- Shah consistently championed public welfare across political roles.
- His unbiased service, particularly to Khairpur's marginalized communities, exemplified accessible leadership.
- Being a renowned personality of politics, he has a well vision of socio economic and its applicable utilization at its regional and sub-regional development.
- During the research study, interviews, surveys, it is confirmed the transparency in democracy, as in debate in parliaments and the constitutional management, that this veteran personality found as the pillar of strength.
- It was also observed during the research study that confirms the transparent policies for alleviation of poverty and took efforts to secure the public revenue in Sindh, Pakistan.
- Further, data revealed that during his tenure ship, the district Khairpur much yielded in the history through doing establishing works, which are easily be seen with naked eyes.

Recommendations

It is further recommended that the unfinished projects to complete the roads might be completed on first priority basis as the agricultural goods could reach at their proper market value. As this district is known as the Queen of dates that may not be devalue the quality and quantity of the dry or semi dry dates as the growers may be benefitted accordingly through its proper exportation.

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Interview conducted with Dr. Samar Razza Talpur, Director I.B.A, Institute of Emerging Technologies Khairpur on Friday Feb., 14.2020.

Interview conducted with Engineer Abdul Naeem Shaikh dated Feb., 18.2020 at Khairpur Special Economic Zone.

Interview conducted with Ghulam Hussain Mughal on Thursday Feb., 06.2020 at his residence, Hadad Mahal Khairpur city.

Interview conducted with Lal Bux Mangi on Saturday Feb., 15.2020, at his residence, Ali Shah Colony, Khairpur city.

Interview conducted with Prof. Dr. Imdad Hussain Sahito (Ex-Dean, Faculty of Social Sciences, SALU- Khairpur) dated April, 01.2024 at Khairpur Mir's at his home, Sahito House, at Shah Abdul Latif University, Housing Society, Khairpur Mir's.

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